

Studies on Ylides : Part III. Synthesis of Olefins via Phosphonate Modification of Wittig Reaction.

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0, 0-Dimethyl 9-fluorenylphosphonate carbanion and 0, 0-dimethyl diphenylmethylphosphonate carbanion have been generated and reacted with a series of substituted aromatic aldehydes and acetone to yield olefins. IR and NMR data for the products are reported.

THE amazing stability and reactivity of fluorenylidenedimethylsulfurane (1a)¹, fluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane (1b)², diphenylmethylenedimethylsulfurane (2a)³ and diphenylmethylenetriphenylphosphorane (2b)⁴ has been the subject of considerable interest in recent years. The unique stability of these ylides has been attributed to the structural and electronic factors which contribute to the stabilization of the ylidic carbanion. This has been thought to result from the delocalization of the non-bonded electrons of the carbanion and the use of the vacant 3d-orbitals of the adjacent heteroatom. These reports, following our previous researches on the reactivity of ylide carbanions⁴⁻⁷, tempted us to examine the reactivity of analogous phosphonate carbanions (3a and 3b) towards carbonyl compounds.

1 a, X = (C₁₃H₉)₂S

1 b, X = (C₆H₅)₂P

2 a, X = (CH₃)₂S

2 b, X = (C₆H₅)₂P

Results and Discussion

Treatment of trimethylphosphite with 9-bromofluorene and diphenylmethyl bromide at 150°C gave 0,0-dimethyl 9-fluorenylphosphonate (4a) and 0,0-dimethyl diphenylmethylphosphonate (4b) respectively in good yields. An exothermic reaction accompanied with the formation of red or pink colouration indicated the generation of phosphonate carbanions (3a) and (3b), which was effected by the proton abstraction from their respective phosphonates (4a) and (4b) with a slurry of sodium hydride in tetrahydrofuran (THF).

The reaction of phosphonate carbanion (3a) with a series of mono- and di-substituted benzaldehydes

(Scheme 1), carried out at 100°C, gave 55-90% yields of benzofluorenes (5a-5k). Similarly the reaction of 3a with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and terephthaldehyde was successful at elevated temperature to give olefin (5l) and bis-exocyclic olefin(6). The carbanion 3a also reacted energetically with acetone under the same reaction conditions affording olefinic product(7) in fair yield.

Similarly the reactivity of phosphonate carbanion (3b) in phosphonate olefination reaction was examined by the treatment of anion 3b with a range of carbonyl compounds. Thus, when a suspension of carbanion 3b was allowed to react with various substituted benzaldehydes (Scheme 2), at 60°C, 1, 1, 2-triaryl substituted ethylenes (8a-8h) were obtained in appreciable yields.

A study of the reactivity of the carbanions (3a) and (3b) towards carbonyl compounds indicates that both the carbanions are comparatively more reactive olefin forming reagents than that of analogous triphenylphosphonium ylides (1b) and (2b)^{2, 4} respectively. Both the carbanions (3a) and (3b) reacted energetically with all the carbonyl compounds in equal potency to afford better yields of olefinic products, thus showing an enhanced nucleophilicity of the carbanionic centres because of the operation of inductive effect of (CH₃O)₂P(O) group and partial double bond character of P(O) linkage.

All the olefins (5a-8h) synthesized in this study are listed in Table 1. It gave correct elemental analysis and their melting points were in accordance with that reported in literature.

The structural assignments of the olefinic products are based on IR and NMR spectral data. The IR spectra (KBr) of the exocyclic olefins (5a-7) recorded characteristic absorption bands at 1625 cm⁻¹ (ν C=C) and at 930 cm⁻¹, whereas in the case of 1, 1, 2-triaryl-substituted ethylenes (8a-8h) absorptions occurred near

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Scheme 1

- 5a, R=C₆H₅; 5b, R=4-OCH₃C₆H₄; 5c, R=3-OCH₃C₆H₄;
 5d, R=4-CH₃C₆H₄; 5e, R=4-OH C₆H₄; 5f, R=2-OH C₆H₄;
 5g, R=4-ClC₆H₄; 5h, R=2,4-(Cl)₂ C₆H₃; 5i, R=2-OH-5-BrC₆H₃;
 5j, R=4-NO₂C₆H₄; 5k, R=3-NO₂C₆H₄; 5l, R=2-OH-1-naphthyl;

Scheme 2

- 8a, Ar=C₆H₅; 8b, Ar=4-OCH₃C₆H₄; 8c, Ar=2-OCH₃C₆H₄;
 8d, Ar=4-CH₃C₆H₄; 8e, Ar=2,4-(Cl)₂C₆H₃;
 8f, Ar=4-OHC₆H₅; 8g, Ar=4-NO₂C₆H₄; 8h, Ar=2-NO₂C₆H₄.

1600 cm⁻¹ (ν C=C) and at 3050 cm⁻¹. The NMR spectra (CDCl₃) of the olefins (5a-8h), in general exhibited a complex pattern of absorptions of olefinic and aromatic protons in between δ6.80-8.33 ppm.

Experimental

Melting points were measured on a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infracord spectrophotometer in KBr. The NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were run using a Varian A-60 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. Analytical samples were purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina. Purity was checked by TLC.

Preparation of O, O-dimethyl 9-fluorenylphosphonate (4a) :

A mixture of 12.25 g (0.05 mole) of 9-bromofluorene and 6.20g (0.05 mole) of trimethylphosphite was heated on an oil bath under nitrogen at 150°C for 14h. The methyl bromide formed during the reaction and unreacted trimethylphosphite was evaporated off under vacuum and the residue 16.5 g (80%) of phosphonate (4a) was extracted with ether. The analytical sample was twice recrystallized from n-hexane to give white crystals, m.p. 109-110°C (Lit.⁶ 109-110°C). NMR absorption δ 3.50 (6H, (OCH₃)₂, duplet), δ 4.52 (1H, methylene duplet), J_{PH}=30 cps and δ 7.20-8.20 (8H, aromatic multiplet) (C₁₅H₁₄O₃P).

Found : C, 65.68 ; H, 5.45, Calcd : C, 65.69 ; H, 5.47%

Preparation of O, O-dimethyl diphenylmethylphosphonate (4b) :

Using above procedure was prepared phosphonate (4b) from 7.44g (0.03 mole) of diphenylmethyl bromide and 3.72g (0.03 mole) of trimethylphosphite in 7.7 g (70%) yield as pale yellow crystals by crystallization from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 95-96°C (Lit.⁶ 96-97°C). IR spectrum (KBr) 1030 cm⁻¹ (ν P-O-C (alkyl)) and 1305 cm⁻¹ (ν P=O) (C₁₅H₁₄O₃P).

Found : C, 64.97 ; H, 6.50, Calcd : C, 64.98 ; H, 6.49%

Reaction of phosphonate carbanion (3a) with aromatic aldehydes :

A general procedure was used in all the reactions. To an intense red suspension of phosphonate carbanion, generated from 2.74 g (0.01 mole) of phosphonate (4a) and 50% slurry of sodium hydride (0.24g ; 0.01 mole) in THF (100 ml), was added in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen, 0.01 mole of aromatic aldehyde and the mixture was stirred at 100°C for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled at room temperature and excess of cold water was added to precipitate a solid which was extracted with ether, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated under reduced pressure. The resulting residual mass was chromatographed to give exocyclic olefin (5a-6). It was further purified by crystallization from appropriate solvent (Table 1).

Reaction of phosphonate carbanion (3a) with acetone :

To a suspension of carbanion (3a), prepared from 2.47g (0.01 mole) of phosphonate (4a) and sodium

TABLE I—STRUCTURE AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF OLEFINS (5a-8h).

(5a-7)

Compound	Yield (%)	Recrystn. solvent	m.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis Found / Calcd (%)	
				C	H
5a	75	EtOH	72-74 ^a	94.47	5.50
5b	80	Hexane	130-31 ^b	94.48	5.51
				88.70	5.60
5c	70	EtOH	145-46	88.73	5.63
				88.68	5.62
5d	65	Hexane	82-84	88.73	5.63
				94.00	5.96
5e	55	C ₆ H ₆ - Hexane	108-9 ^c	94.03	5.97
				88.86	5.15
5f	50	CHCl ₃ - Hexane	66-67	88.88	5.18
				88.87	5.17
5g	75	EtOH	148-50 ^d	88.86	5.18
				83.16	4.48
5h	80	EtOH	110-1 ₁	83.18	4.50
				74.28	3.68
5i	60	CHCl ₃ - Hexane	193-97	74.30	3.71
				72.04	3.89
5j	90	EtOH	167-68 ^e	72.07	3.90
				80.23	4.32
5k	85	EtOH - H ₂ O	110-11	80.26	4.34
				80.24	4.32
5l	52	EtOH (80%)	117-18	80.26	4.34
				89.98	5.00
6	70	DMF	212-14 ^f	90.00	5.00
				94.86	5.07
7	50	EtOH	68	94.88	5.11
				93.17	6.74
				93.20	6.79

(8a-8h)

8a	75	EtOH	68-69 ^g	93.74	6.23
8b	68	EtOH - H ₂ O	81-82 ^h	93.75	6.25
				88.10	6.28
8c	66	EtOH	86-88 ⁱ	88.11	6.29
				88.08	6.28
8d	55	CHCl ₃ - Hexane	70-71 ^j	88.11	6.29
				93.31	6.64
8e	65	EtOH (90%)	144-46	93.33	6.66
				73.84	4.29
8f	55	C ₆ H ₆ - Hexane	140-42	73.84	4.30
				88.20	5.87
8g	95	EtOH	152-52 ^k	88.23	5.88
				79.70	4.97
8h	90	EtOH	131 ^l	79.73	4.98
				79.72	4.96
				79.73	4.98

a, Lit.⁹ 71-74°C, b, Lit.⁹ 129.5-131°C, c, Lit.¹⁰ 112°C, d, Lit.⁹ 147-48°C, e, Lit.⁹ 167-68°C, f, Lit.¹¹ 216°C, g, Lit.¹³ 70.5-71.5°C, h, Lit.¹³ 81-82°C, i, Lit.¹² 80.5-82.0°C, j, Lit.¹³ 70-71°C, k, Lit.¹² 153-54°C, l, Lit.¹² 133°C.

hydride (50%, 0.01 mole) in THF (10 ml), was added, under nitrogen, 0.58g (0.01 mole) of acetone. The reaction mixture was stirred at 60°C for 16h and general procedure was followed to afford 1.5g (50%) 1,1-dimethyl-9-fluorenylidene (7) (Table 1).

Reaction of phosphonate carbanion (3b) with substituted benzaldehydes :

To a solution of phosphonate (4b) (2.77g, 0.01 mole) in 100 ml of THF was added 0.24g (0.01 mole) of 50% sodium hydride. The suspension was stirred at room temperature under nitrogen for half an hour. An exothermic reaction accompanied with the formation of pale yellow colour was observed. To this coloured solution was added dropwise a solution of 0.01 mole of substituted benzaldehyde in 20 ml of THF. After the complete addition the reaction temperature was allowed to rise to 60-70°C for additional 12h and general procedure was followed. The 1, 1, 2-triarylsusbstituted ethylenes (8a-h) obtained as crystalline coloured solids are listed in Table 1.

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